

5 August 2024 :

Dear Dr Fontana,

I am writing to you about your submission to COPE regarding concerns about the publication in *Frontiers in Marine Science* titled 'Reconstructing Global Chlorophyll-a Variations Using a Non-linear Statistical Approach'. I would be grateful if you could please provide some clarification about the concerns you would like COPE to review:

- I understand that you indicated you had been included as an author without your knowledge or permission. The journal has issued a Correction to remove you from the author list. Given that the authorship concern has been addressed, can you please indicate what concern about the publication you would like COPE to review?
- The Pubpeer thread you referred to includes a copy of a communication indicating that legal counsel had been engaged, can you please clarify whether any legal procedures are active about this matter? If previous legal action has been concluded, can you clarify what the outcome was of that process?

Please note that any review undertaken by the Facilitation and Integrity subcommittee is focused on the procedural aspects of the journal's follow up, and we will not complete evaluations of the scholarly content of the article, or adjudicate on the authorship of publications. Per the expectations of the Facilitation and Integrity process, we expect that there will be no public commentary about this matter (for example, on social media, blogging sites, Pubpeer or other) while the issue is active with COPE.

With best wishes,

XXXXXX

5 August 2024 :

Dear XXXXXX,

Frontiers always refused to retract and removing my name was the only option I was proposed, so I took it.

So I obtained an authorship change form with signature of every participants.

There was a justice complaint against me for moral harassment by the first author when I complained actually. It's crazy ... !

COPE guidelines were clearly violated by authors as well as by Frontiers as my name was used without authorization as an erroneous mail was provided upon submission.

I can provide any further details and a lot are already on PubPeer.

I put integrity officer of Frontiers in cc, you can see directly with them as they follow your "guidelines".

Thank you very much and best regards,

Clement

9 August 2024

Dear Dr Fontana,

Thank you for your response and for clarifying that there are no active legal procedures in relation to this matter.

Please note that the remit of the COPE Facilitation and Integrity is strictly focused on a review of the process pursued by the journal to follow up on concerns raised to their attention. COPE cannot adjudicate on matters related to authorship or make determinations on the contributions made by individuals to a particular manuscript or publication.

From the information you have supplied, and looking at the procedural aspects of the authorship concerns for the article, the journal followed the COPE guideline indicating that all parties should be approached, and if agreement is reached a Correction should be published:

<https://publicationethics.org/>

With regard to concerns about plagiarism, the COPE flowchart indicates that if the matter cannot be resolved through communication with the authors, the journal should consider approaching the institution for an investigation: <https://publicationethics.org/>. The information posted on Pubpeer makes reference to an institutional investigation, can you please clarify whether such investigation took place in relation to your plagiarism concerns, and if so, what the ruling was from that institutional review?

Thank you for this further clarification.

With best wishes,

XXXXXX

12 August 2024

Dear XXXXXX,

Thank you very much for taking the time to manage this matter.

I put the PubPeer link here for clarity (I'll refer to it below) :

<https://pubpeer.com/>

Concerning the use of my name :

The only fact that my name was used without my consent is a serious breach to publication ethics. The normal procedure is a retraction if concerned author ask for it. See PubPeer link #10 for an example, you can find many others on RetractionWatch database.

*This article has been retracted at the request of the stated author Zachary Grasley. **Zachary Grasley did not consent to being added as a co-author on this paper**, he was not informed of the submission to the journal as an erroneous email address was provided (...) the corresponding author is in breach of the journal's ethical policy.*

This is exactly the same situation for Elsevier, and Elsevier follows the COPE guidelines. (<https://www.elsevier.com/>)

Frontiers follows the COPE guidelines too, but the only option I was proposed was to remove my name.

This means I contest the publication of this paper, but I do not give up the work I done.

Also, an erroneous email was provided (clement.fontana@ird.fr), why authors did not try to get in touch with me while we knew well and worked together ? This is not the correct procedure at all.

Concerning the plagiarism aspect :

The situation is quite complicated so here is a short timeline :

August 2016 - February 2018 : I worked 18 months for the Institut Français de Développement (IRD) under the supervision of the corresponding author of the concerned paper. I wrote the first version of the paper as first author but it was never published as my contract was not renewed. Please notice that the corresponding author indicates on a website that I was the "*main researcher involved*" in the project (PubPeer #9).

You can see in the document I sent [retraction_request.pdf](#) all the similarities between text/figures of both versions.

July 2020 : I discovered the paper online a few weeks after its publication and I immediately contacted Frontiers to say that I did not agree with the publication of this content and the use of my name without my permission. Frontiers told me they were opening an investigation.

December 2020 : Frontiers recognizes the situation was problematic and asked me to search for an agreement with the main authors institute (IRD).

May 2021 : I sent an official letter written by a lawyer to reach an agreement with the institute, as I consider this paper infringes my career and the benefits I should have get from this paper if it has been published differently. Please notice that I asked a lawyer in order to be sure to respect every procedural aspect.

October 2021 : IRD answered me an official lawyer letter saying they will not propose any agreement. Following this, I sent to Frontiers the documents retraction_request.pdf to formally ask for the paper retractrion and to expose every details showing this paper does not respect their chart (e.g. PubPeer #3)

December 2021 : An Integrity Officer (IO) was nominated by the IRD and he immediately contacted me to propose a neutral procedure for everybody to expose our arguments, which I accepted.

January 2022 : The IO finally indicates me that he was warned by the judirical division of a risk and so he will not interfere in the matter (PubPeer #7). So no, no investigation was never performed by the institute. IRD would be unable to show you any evidence that an investigation was ever performed.

February 2022 : The Frontiers research integrity team wrote me they will not retract as the IRD IO asked them not to retract (PubPeer #6). So on one hand, the IRD IO did not want to interfere with me as the situation presented a juridical risk, but on the other hand he interfered directly with Frontiers to oppose the retraction.

May 2024 : Frontiers proposed me to remove my name from this paper, and a form was signed by all authors.

Of course I do not expect COPE to judge the scholarly aspects, but I have a few points I would like you to consider and answer.

I think it could also be important for other persons in such a situation.

Frontiers told me that following the COPE, the institute (IRD) is responsible of managing the matter.

I could understand if every authors work in the same institution that it should be managed internally.

But this is not the case here as I left this position more than 2 years before the paper was published. I could never have imagined that authors could publish this work without getting in touch with me.

So the institute and me are clearly in conflict on this paper and I don't understand why they should decide if it is plagiarism or not.

Simply speaking, I accuse them of plagiarism and they can decide if it is plagiarism or not.

IRD is both part of the conflict, and judge and a fair procedure was not respected (PubPeer #18 and #19).

To me, they are clearly not neutral as their interest is to protect their researchers and their image. Frontiers should have manage the matter and asked a few experts to give a neutral point of view and propose a clear report.

Please also notice in this situation that I was (and still is) the only contractual researcher in the author list while all other authors are permanent.

To me this story represents a serious infringement to contractual researchers if they have not any way to defend their rights.

I still consider this as a serious danger for the good progress of research, and more generally science.

I would really like to have the COPE point-of-view on these last points.

It will be too long to put here but you can ask me for every documents/contacts to prove my claims.

Thank you again and best regards,

Clément

2 September 2024

Dear Dr Fontana,

I am writing to follow up on the concerns you raised to COPE regarding the article in *Frontiers in Marine Science* titled 'Reconstructing Global Chlorophyll-a Variations Using a Non-linear Statistical Approach'. We have looked at the details of the concerns you shared, and we do not feel this matter comes within the remit of what the COPE Facilitation and Integrity Subcommittee can review.

You have raised concerns about the fact that you were listed as an author without your permission, and about the fact that you allege that the article includes content related to your earlier contributions to the project.

As previously noted, any review by the COPE Facilitation and Integrity is strictly focused on a review of the process pursued by the journal to follow up on concerns raised to their attention. From the information you shared, the journal pursued follow up on your concerns via communications with you and the other authors, and when all parties agreed to a change in authorship to remove your name as an author, the journal completed a Correction to the record to implement that change. Those steps are aligned to the COPE guidance outlined here: <https://publicationethics.org/>

You have raised concerns about plagiarism in the article, however, plagiarism arises when an individual presents another person's work as their own and without proper acknowledgement. In this case, your contribution was acknowledged through authorship, and this acknowledgement was removed following your agreement. The COPE Retraction guidelines note that retraction is not appropriate where '*authorship is disputed but there is no reason to doubt the validity of the findings*'. From a procedural point of view, if the editors did not have concerns about the integrity

of the article content or the study's conclusions, there is no expectation for them to correct the record beyond the Correction to authorship agreed by the different parties. In light of this, there is no procedural deviation in the journal's follow up that we can review in this instance, and we cannot pursue this matter.

Thank you for raising this matter to the attention of COPE.

With best wishes,

XXXXXX Puebla

2 September 2024

Der XXXXXX,

You state :

"You have raised concerns about plagiarism in the article, however, plagiarism arises when an individual presents another person's work as their own and without proper acknowledgement. In this case, your contribution was acknowledged through authorship"

Well, this is exactly the case and I don't consider that my contribution was properly "*acknowledged through authorship*" actually.

You can see on this website : <https://emartinez550.wixsite>.

That I am listed as the main contributor of the project :

Main researchers involved: C. Fontana UMR EIO; T. Gorgues UMR LOPS ; M. Lengaigne UMR LOCEAN.

So that being listed as the 4th author without being informed of the submission is not a "*proper acknowledgement*" to me and I still feel like my intellectual properties was violated by my ex-colleagues.

Once again, why authors did not try to contact me ? I answer you : obviously because I would have refused the submission in such a manner. This is why they did not contact me.

1/ Does COPE validate the way to proceed, *i.e.* putting an author in the list without informing him/her of the submission ?

As I already told you, putting me as 4th author without my approval and indicating a wrong mail is in total contradiction with Frontiers policy (<https://www.frontiersin.org/>) and more generally basic ethical rules :

Provide approval for publication of the content

2/ By curiosity, did Frontiers or the concerned institute was able to provide you any kind of report showing that a neutral investigation was conducted ?

Also, on the COPE site I can read here : <https://publicationethics.org/case/authorship-dispute-5>

There may be a case for retraction of the paper based on plagiarism, if co-authors C, D, and E claim it was their work, and then the other authors have taken that work and published it as their own.

3/ Could you explain me the difference between this case and mine ?

I really would like to have the position of COPE for points 1/, 2/ and 3/.

Thank you and best regards,

Clément

2 September 2024

Dear XXXXXX,

I would like to add a 4th point, maybe it could help you for equivalent cases.

4/ To summarize, I worked 18 months for an institute and was 100% involved in this sole project. I wrote a close-to-submission draft as 1st author. My contract was not renewed so I left without submitting it.

My ex-colleagues took this draft, did some slight modifications and published it without informing me (providing a wrong mail), with me as 4th author. This is in agreement with the COPE guidelines ?

Best regards,

Clément

5 September 2024

Dear XXXXXX,

I was just thinking about this.

Finally, the authorship problem is fixed because my name is removed from author list.

And there is no plagiarism problem because their was my name in the author list.

This is serious ?

Could you please ask your "facilitator" to seriously reconsider the situation ?

Best regards,

Clément

9 September

Dear Dr Fontana,

I acknowledge receipt of your emails over the last week. I consulted with the member of the Facilitation and Integrity subcommittee in relation to your response and your remaining concerns. The position remains that the matters you raised fall beyond the remit of what the subcommittee can review.

As we previously indicated, any review by the COPE Facilitation and Integrity subcommittee is strictly focused on the procedural aspects of the journal's follow up. From the information you have supplied, you have remaining concerns about the use of your contributions in the article. COPE cannot review or adjudicate on matters related to individual contributions to an article, or to specific parts of scholarly content in the publication, as such matters require a full review by the relevant institution(s). It is also beyond the subcommittee's review to comment on or interfere with institutional review processes.

Your concerns fall beyond the scope of the subcommittee and as a result, we are not in a position to comment on the contributions to the work or your allegations of plagiarism, and we cannot pursue a review of your submission.

Sincerely,

XXXXXX

13 Septembre

Dear XXXXXX,

Thank you for answer. Sorry to bother you again, this will be my last email.

You state :

"it is also beyond the subcommittee's review to comment on or interfere with institutional review processes."

Once again this was not my institute (!) and their researchers plagiarized my work.

The "*review process*" should not be let the institute as it is both part and judge in this conflict. The "*review process*" should be neutral, and performed by a third party with no interest into the matter.

This does not respect your flowchart here :

<https://publicationethics.org/sites/default/files/plagiarism-submitted-manuscript-cope-flowchart.pdf>

And you will no make me believe the inverse.

Thank you anyway for the time you spent for not-review this case.

Regards,

Clément